

ANALYSIS OF GARDEN SOIL ALGOFLORA

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Abstract: The article provides information on the types and species of soil algae determined from soil samples taken from the soil of vineyards and orchards from 0-5 cm to a depth of 20-25 cm.

Key word: Vineyard, essential garden, soil algae, species and species, gray soil.

Cultivated soils are fundamentally different from non-cultivated conservation lands. When soil is plowed and cultivated, its biological properties, in particular, biogenicity, biological activity, and productivity increase. When the soil is cultivated, the number of microorganisms in it increases, the importance of mold fungi decreases, and nitrification processes increase. That's why we conducted scientific research on the study of soil algae.

Processing the soil with different methods leads to a change in the order of algae communities in it [1; 389-399.]. Algae of cultivated soils are very dynamic, therefore there are many similarities in the flora of algae in different geographical regions. To date, there is information in the literature about the effect of soil cultivation: plowing, cultivation, fertilization, application of various insecticides, land reclamation, and even cultivation on the composition of algae flora and their development. First of all, this is manifested in the composition of algosinusia of each crop [2; 212-215.]. It was studied that the types of cyanobacteria and algae in the vineyards and orchards designated for research consist of the following species. 58 species were identified from vineyard soils, which made up 30% of the total species (194) in the fields where algological research was conducted. In Almazor soils, this indicator is 24.21%. In the taxonomic structure, the shares of cyanobacteria and green algae have the same index. The number of species of diatom algae in Almazor soils made up 37.0% of the species identified from this place. In vineyard soils, this indicator is 24.14%. [3; 47.]. Cyanobacteria took the first place with 37.37 percent more than others in field soils where algoflora was studied. A similar figure is 33.68% of diatom algae. These two comprise 71.05% of the total algoflora. Green algae make up 24.73% of the total algoflora. Among the groups of algae, representatives of the department Xanthophyta make up only 4.21%.

Table 1

Changes in the number of species of cyanobacteria and eukaryotic algae in vineyard and orchard soils (1st plowed, 2nd plowed layer)

Departments of algae	vineyard			essential garden		
	Autumn (October)		Total	Autumn (October)		Total
	1	2		1	2	
Cyanobacteria	20	3	20	14	9	14
Chlorophyta	20	6	20	13	2	13
Xanthophyta	4	1	4	2	1	2
Bacillariophyta	14	3	14	17	6	17
Total	58	13	58	46	18	46

The analysis of the given numerical data shows that the maximum conditions for the development of algae do not exist in the perennial vineyard and mulberry soils without irrigation in the one-year wheat field. Contrary to this situation, soil fertilization and moisture preservation in cotton fields and alfalfa fields allow the development of algae groups. This situation increased to a maximum during the summer when the temperature and humidity were sufficient. [4; 232-236, 5; 98-101].

The general list of algae found in vineyard and orchard soils was unique for both fields. The samples include *Merismopedia tenuissima*, *Gloeocapsa punctata*, *Nostok linckia f. muscorum*, *Phormidium foveolarum*, *Ph. frigidum*, *Lyngbya martensiana f. edaphyca*, *Chlorococcum humicola*, *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Chlorhormidium dissectum va Tribonema elegans* developed well. For diamond soils, *Nostoc commune f. sphaericum*, *Anabaena cylindrical f. hollerbachiana*, *Phormidium incinatum*, *Ph. corium*, *Chlamydomonas globosa*, *Pinnularia silvatica* and others became characteristic. 13 species were identified in samples of vineyard soil below of its plowed layer.

Conclusions, the soil algoflora of the vineyard and essential garden soils kept almost similar species and species. The reason for this is that the almost identical agrotechnical measures and the lack of irrigation have led to the development of less number of algae cells. 11 types and species were identified under the plowed layer of essential garden soil. For its soil, *Nostoc commune f.*

sphaericum, *Anabaena cylindrical f. hollerbachiana*, *Phormidium incinatum*, *Ph. corium*, *Chlamydomonas globose*, *Pinnularia silvatica* and others became characteristic.

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